

Technology of Organizing Monitoring of the Physical Development of Preschool Children

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Annotation: Physical education of children is carried out by the whole team of employees in the organization of work on physical education in pre-school educational organizations. This article contains recommendations on the technology of organizing the monitoring of the physical development of children of preschool age.

Keywords: preschool education, pedagogy, physiological changes, motivation, psychophysiological state, individuality, "psychological health".

Introduction

One of the main tasks is to raise and form a healthy generation, which is the national essence of universal human values, and sports and physical education have become a state policy. This factor is the essence of the national concept of physical education and sports. Physical education and sports are a necessary daily need for citizens of all ages. The theory of physical education takes an important place due to its close connection with intellectual, moral, aesthetic and labor education.

Discussion and Results

The specific characteristics of the development of preschool children and the tasks and goals of physical education are to educate the young generation as a healthy, comprehensively developed person based on the ideology of independence and to prepare them for school education. The main tasks of educating children of preschool age are to develop children physically, mentally and spiritually, to prepare them for regular education (school) based on national and universal values, taking into account their innate abilities, interest, needs and opportunities. It is certainly gratifying that it has risen to the level of state politics. The tasks of physical education of children of preschool age are the only goal of all branches of the physical education system: to prepare children for life, work and defense of the Motherland.

The tasks of physical education of children of preschool age are given taking into account their age characteristics.

The following tasks of physical education in preschool educational organizations are:

1. Sanitation tasks.
2. Educational tasks.
3. Preservation of life and strengthening of health.

In the period of technical development of physical education tools, great importance is attached to physical education and sports. Because, in the era of technical progress,

humanity is freed from physical labor and suffers from the most dangerous disease of "inactivity", which leads to diseases of the blood-vascular system. Therefore, the Decrees on physical education and children's sports issued by our state in recent years are evidence of concern for children's spiritual and physical development, their health, hardworking and happiness. Therefore, it is important to use physical education tools for the physical and comprehensive development of children.

Gymnastics is a specially selected exercise system that affects the child's body in every way, strengthens its main physiological processes, and helps in harmonious development. Thanks to gymnastics exercises, vital movement skills, beauty and accuracy of movements are formed, basic physical qualities - agility, quickness, strength, endurance, flexibility are developed. Gymnastics is used from early childhood and is continued throughout the entire young age of a person's life. Action games are considered as the main means of physical education, and children's movement activities have a creative effect on the physical development of children, on the formation of movement skills and physical qualities, on the strengthening of health by increasing the functional activity of the body and increasing feelings of emotional joy.

The healing effect achieved by active games is inextricably linked with the positive emotions that arise during children's play and have a positive effect on the child's psyche. It is advisable to change the action games. However, variety is not only to keep the children interested in the game, but also to improve the pedagogical tasks and actions, perform some complex game actions, and change the conditions of the game situation. It is also necessary to educate their qualities. It requires them to have a certain mental and physical strength and, at the same time, a growing interest in the game. Physical exercises and sports games and exercises play an important role in the organization of children's movement activities. Skiing, skating, sledding, riding a bicycle, scooter, sports roller, as well as swimming belong to sports exercises. All of them help to strengthen the main muscle groups, develop the bone, cardiovascular, respiratory and nervous systems. In addition, during training, children develop physical qualities (agility, quickness, endurance, etc.), as well as rhythmicity, coordination of movements, and the ability to aim in space. Riding a bicycle, skating develops vestibular stability.

Forms of organization of physical education in MTT, physical education classes as the main form of regular training of children in physical exercises, the classes are fun, disciplined, able to move well in the environment, fast and confident in accordance with the assigned task, active in a goal-oriented manner serves to educate individuals who can show moral qualities and creativity. The importance of the training is the formation of the culture of action, health, regular implementation of educational and educational tasks. Organization of work on physical education in children's daily life. Action games are the main movement activity of preschool children, as well as physical exercises, planned by the educator at different times of the day, according to the agenda of each age group: in the morning, at noon, and during the evening walk.

Conclusion

In the distribution of games, the educator takes into account the variety of movement content, the necessary repetition and complexity, which serve to improve movement skills.

It is important to take into account the conditions of the external environment and to educate behavior in a specific situation. Physical education of children is carried out by the entire team of employees in the organization of work on physical education in pre-school educational organizations. All employees, from the principal to the technical staff, are encouraged to protect the life and health of every child, as well as solve other tasks of physical education.

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